

ANALOGY AS INSTRUCTIONAL STRATEGY IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF CRITICAL THINKING SKILLS OF GRADE 9 STUDENTS

SARAH JOY C. GUTIERREZ¹

LUCILA C. PALACIO²

sarahjoy.gutierrez@deped.gov.ph

<https://orcid.org/0000-0001-7628-7923>

Laguna State Polytechnic University-San Pablo Campus Brgy. Del Remedio, San Pablo City, Laguna, Philippines

ABSTRACT

This research paper entitled “Analogy as Instructional Strategy in the Development of Critical thinking Skills of Grade 9 Students” is an approach to know if analogies can develop critical thinking skills of grade 9 students in Araling Panlipunan 9 – Ekonomiks in which the researcher considers as significant in providing recommendations anchored to the research findings. The aim of the study is to know the perceived level of understanding about analogy and critical thinking, the significant difference of the pretest of posttest after analogy is used, and the significant relationship of analogy and critical thinking skills. It is a Descriptive Experimental type of research which applied frequency, average weighted mean, standard deviation, t-test and Pearson r correlation to analyze and interpret data. The following are the findings of the study: The respondents “agreed” that opposite analogy, cause and effect analogy, problem and solution analogy, object and function analogy, and performer and action analogy can develop their critical thinking skills. The result of their pretest has fall to “did not meet expectations” while the posttest result was described as follows: “fairly satisfactory” in analyzing, “satisfactory” in comparing and contrasting, “fairly satisfactory” in problem solving and “did not meet expectations in evaluating”. Based on the findings, the following conclusion were derived: There is a significant difference between the pretest and posttest result in critical thinking in terms of analyzing, comparing and contrasting, problem solving, and evaluating for the respondents have shown improvement on the test scores. There is no significant relationship between the used analogies and critical thinking skills aside for the object and function analogy and evaluating which was the only parameter that show better improvement while the others have improve but not enough to say that it really affect each other.

Keywords: Economics, Analogy Strategy, Critical thinking, experimental research, Philippines